

chambers are twice as deep as the main tank and always contain water. They are connected by "T" pieces that direct the water flow from the top of one chamber to the bottom of the next. If significant numbers of the nematodes survive successive sedimentation, they can be killed by adding formaldehyde to the chambers. Water leaving the last sedimentation chamber is directed into

an open drain with an independent water supply, which may be used to dilute any chemical treatment.

In 1979, a successful infestation was achieved in a plot (8 X 8 m) by incorporating 1.5 infested panicles/m² with the surface soil at sowing in early April; the subsequent rice crop was almost totally lost because of ufra.

Miniature deepwater tanks (IRRN 4:3), which provide total exclusion, or polythene cages, which prevent the mass movement of nematodes between adjacent plots, may be used to segregate individual plots from water in the main tank. The main tank can also be used to study other methods of ufra control such as transplanting. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Cold tolerance

Effect of low temperature on boro rice in West Bengal

2 *S. K. Bardhan Roy and S. Biswas, Rice Research Station (RRS), Chinsurah, West Bengal, India*

The dry season (boro) rice crop on the Gangetic Plains of West Bengal is subject to low-temperature stress, which inhibits normal plant growth and delays maturity (av min day/night temperature is 25.2/9.2°C – 28.8/14.9°C). The possibility of minimizing the effect of cold by using tolerant varieties and modified agronomic practices was investigated at the Chinsurah RRS.

The more important results are summarized:

- When seeds are sown on 12 November, 26 November, and 10 December (the traditional sowing time), seedling height gradually decreases, regardless of variety, as temperature falls (av min 17.4–9.7°C). But seedlings sown in mid-November have the proper height and higher dry-matter content at 45 days after sowing. That facilitates transplanting.

- Low temperature delays seedling leaf emergence by as long as 30 days. As seedlings grow older, the effect of low temperature disappears; regardless of variety and sowing time, the 4-leaf stage occurs at 45 days after sowing.

- Seedlings sown in mid-November (25.5/9.6°C – 29.0/14.4°C) have higher ultimate plant height and number of

fertile tillers than seedlings sown in early December.

- The crop sown in early December has a shorter growth duration than that sown earlier. Early flowering causes high spikelet sterility. Seed fertility is higher under a diurnal temperature range of 31.5/20.1°C – 33.5/22.4°C during panicle initiation to flowering, which occurs in the second week of March, regardless of variety or sowing date.

- Mid-November sowing gives higher yields for all the varieties. Yields of crops sown on 26 November and 10 December were 22 and 30% lower, respectively.

- Among several high yielding varieties tested, CR126-42-1 showed the best general adaptability for boro. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Influence of insecticide sprays on brown planthopper resurgence

2 *S. Ghelliah, entomologist, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, India, and E. A. Heinrichs, entomologist, International Rice Research Institute*

An IRRI experiment was conducted to determine the effect of the last insecticide in a series of three spray applications in inducing BPH resurgence.

Ten-day-old TN1 seedlings were planted at 2 seedlings/pot in clay pots 12 cm in diameter. The potted plants

were kept insect free. Sprays were prepared in water from commercial formulations of emulsifiable concentrates at 0.04% concentration (except decamethrin, for which 0.002% was used). The quantity of spray fluid required per plot – at 500 liters/ha – was based on field recommendations.

Ten days after planting, the first insecticide was sprayed. The potted plants were placed on an electrically operated revolving table and the insecticide was sprayed with an atomizer. The plants were sprayed either three times with the same insecticide or one or

two times with one insecticide followed by another insecticide. The plants in each pot were covered with cylindrical mylar film cages and were maintained in an insectary with a regulated temperature of 27 ± 1°C, relative humidity of 60–80%, and photoperiod of 12 hours/day.

Fifteen days after the 3d spraying, 2 gravid BPH females/pot were released and confined with the sprayed plants for 7 days. Sufficient populations of test insects of the same age were maintained on TN1 plants to daily replace dead insects. After 7 days, the insects were

removed and their reproductive rate was assessed indirectly by counting the emerging nymphs from plants that received different insecticides. The counted nymphs were removed every day, and counting went on until all eggs hatched.

The number of nymphs hatching was the criterion for evaluation of the resurgence potential of the insecticides. The number of nymphs differed significantly among treatments (see figure). The highest number emerged from plants sprayed 3 times with decamethrin. The last insecticide sprayed generally had a decisive role in inducing

or preventing BPH resurgence. In treatments where plants were sprayed twice with Perthane and then by decamethrin or methyl parathion the level of BPH resurgence was equal to that where plants were sprayed three times with methyl parathion. When Perthane was sprayed last, the number of BPH nymphs did not increase, regardless of the insecticides used in previous sprayings. This implied that even if resurgence-causing insecticide had inadvertently been used, the population buildup could be controlled by use of an insecticide that would negate the resurgence effect. ■

T. W. Mew, IRRI pathologist, on a September 1979 visit to the institute, suggested that the disease might be caused by *Erwinia* sp. S. Devadath from the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, examined the crop on 31 October and suggested that the disease might be bacterial foot rot caused by *Erwinia chrysanthemi*, which was reported by Goto in Japan in 1979. This may be the first report of the disease in India. The disease is being further investigated. ■

A new record of rice transitory yellowing virus in northern Thailand

H. Inoue, Kyushu National Agricultural Experiment Station, Fukuoka 833; T. Omura, Plant Virus Research Institute, Tsukuba 305; T. Morinaka, Tropical Agriculture Research Center, Tsukuba 305; Y. Saito, Plant Virus Research Institute, Tsukuba 305, Japan; and M. Pytta, D. Chettanachit, A. Parejarearn, S. Disthaporn, S. Kadkao, Department of Agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives, Bangkok 9, Thailand

Yellowing symptoms of rice plants similar to those of rice transitory yellowing disease (RTYV) occurred on wet-season rice at the late growth stage in August–September 1979 in Chiengrai and Chiengmai, northern Thailand. At locations where disease symptoms were observed, 18 to 32% of the hills were infested.

Electromicroscopic observations of dip preparations and ultrathin sections of diseased plants revealed that bullet-shaped virus particles (90 x 120 nm in dip preparations, 90 x 180 nm in ultrathin sections) were similar to those found in diseased leaves infected with RTYV in Taiwan and Okinawa, Japan. In ultrathin sections, the virus particles were observed in phloem cells of diseased plants.

Nephotettix nigropictus and *N. cincticeps* transmitted the virus effectively and in a persistent manner. The virus incubation period in the insects was about 2 weeks; the viruliferous insects often remained infective during their entire life span.

The virus belonging to the rhabdovirus group was identified as rice transitory

The influence of insecticide used in spray sequence on brown planthopper reproductive rate. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University and IRRI.

A new bacterial disease of rice

R. C. Chaudhury and S. M. Ghufan, Rajendra Agricultural University, Bihar Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna 800001, India

Most plants in a 2-ha plot of the variety Pankaj were observed to be drying during a routine field visit to the Institute farm in 1979 kharif. The crop was in the maximum-tillering stage. The growth of the infected plants was somewhat stunted. From a distance the disease appeared to

be the kresak stage of bacterial blight. But a closer examination showed black and rotting basal internodes and enclosing leaf sheaths. The gummy, rotted portion emitted a foul odor. Core portions of tillers dried first; sometimes the central leaf dried much earlier than the other leaves and the symptoms resembled those of stem borer damage. The dried leaves were erect and straw color. Only a few tillers in most infected hills remained healthy. Roots were normal but dried tillers could easily be pulled out.